

INTERNATIONAL MECHANISMS FOR THE PROTECTION OF YOUTH RIGHTS

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Abstract. *“International Mechanisms for the Protection of Youth Rights” explores the multifaceted strategies and mechanisms implemented globally to safeguard the rights and well-being of young people. In this article delves into the framework of international agreements, conventions, and treaties aimed at promoting and protecting the rights of youth across various domains such as education, health, employment, and participation in decision-making processes. It examines the roles of key international organizations like the United Nations, UNESCO, and UNICEF in advocating for youth rights and facilitating collaboration among nations to address challenges faced by young people worldwide. Additionally, the article highlights successful initiatives and ongoing efforts to strengthen youth protection mechanisms, emphasizing the importance of collective action and cross-border cooperation in ensuring a secure and promising future for the world's youth population.*

Keywords: youth rights, human rights, international mechanisms, political, economic, social, cultural rights, of child labor, slavery, trafficking, hazardous work, sexual health.

Аннотация. *“Международные механизмы защиты прав молодежи” исследует многогранные стратегии и механизмы, реализуемые во всем мире для защиты прав и благополучия молодежи. В этой статье рассматриваются рамки международных соглашений, конвенций и международных договоров, направленных на поощрение и защиту прав молодежи в различных областях, таких как образование, здравоохранение, занятость и участие в процессах принятия решений. В нем рассматривается роль ключевых международных организаций, таких как Организация Объединенных Наций, ЮНЕСКО и ЮНИСЕФ, в защите прав молодежи и содействии сотрудничеству между странами для решения проблем, с которыми сталкиваются молодые люди во всем мире. Кроме того, в статье освещаются успешные инициативы и текущие усилия по укреплению механизмов защиты молодежи, подчеркивается важность коллективных действий и трансграничного сотрудничества в обеспечении безопасного и многообещающего будущего для молодежи всего мира.*

Ключевые слова: права молодёж, права человека, международные механизмы, политический, экономический, социальный, культурные права, о детском труде, рабство, торговлю людьми, опасная работа, сексуальная здоровья.

Annotatsiya. *“Yoshlar huquqlarini himoya qilishning xalqaro mexanizmlari” butun dunyo bo‘ylab yoshlarning huquqlari va farovonligini himoya qilish uchun amalga oshirilayotgan ko‘p qirrali strategiya va mexanizmlarni o‘rganadi. Ushbu maqolada, sog‘liqni saqlash, bandlik va qaror qabul qilish jarayonlarida ishtirok etish kabi turli sohalarida yoshlar huquqlarini rag‘batlantirish va himoya qilishga qaratilgan xalqaro shartnomalar, konventsiyalar va xalqaro shartnomalar doirasi ko‘rib chiqiladi. Bunda Birlashgan Millatlar tashkiloti, YUNESKO va UNICEF kabi asosiy xalqaro tashkilotlarning yoshlar huquqlarini himoya qilish va butun dunyo bo‘ylab yoshlar duch keladigan muammolarni hal qilish uchun mamlakatlar o‘rtasidagi hamkorlikni rivojlantirishdagi roli tahlil qilinadi. Bundan tashqari, maqolada yoshlarni himoya qilish mexanizmlarini mustahkamlash bo‘yicha muvaffaqiyatli tashabbuslar va davom etayotgan*

sa'y-harakatlarni ta'kidlaydi, butun dunyo yoshlari uchun xavfsiz va istiqbolli kelajakni ta'minlashda jamoaviy harakatlar va transchegaraviy hamkorlikning muhimligi ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: yoshlar huquqlari, inson huquqlari, xalqaro mexanizmlar, siyosiy, iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy, madaniy huquqlar, bolalar mehnati, qullik, odam savdosi, xavfli mehnat, jinsiy salomatlik.

Youth rights are fundamental human rights that are essential for the development, well-being, and participation of young people in society. These rights encompass various aspects of life, including education, health, participation, protection from violence, and access to opportunities. To ensure the protection of youth rights globally, there are several international mechanisms and instruments in place.

United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC)

One of the most significant international mechanisms for the protection of youth rights is the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC). Adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 1989, the UNCRC sets out the civil, political, economic, social, and cultural rights of children under the age of 18. It covers a wide range of issues, including the right to education, health care, protection from exploitation and abuse, and participation in decisions affecting their lives.

The UNCRC has been ratified by almost every country in the world, making it the most widely ratified human rights treaty in history. As a legally binding instrument, it obligates states parties to take all necessary measures to ensure that children and young people enjoy their rights to the fullest extent possible.

International Labour Organization (ILO) Conventions

The International Labour Organization (ILO) has also developed several conventions aimed at protecting the rights of young workers. These conventions address issues such as child labor, minimum age of employment, and working conditions for young people. For example, the ILO Convention No. 182 on the Worst Forms of Child Labour calls for the prohibition and elimination of the worst forms of child labor, including slavery, trafficking, and hazardous work.

World Health Organization (WHO) Guidelines

The World Health Organization (WHO) provides guidelines and recommendations for the protection of youth rights in the context of health. This includes ensuring access to essential healthcare services, promoting mental health and well-being, and addressing issues such as substance abuse and sexual health.

Council of Europe Framework for the Participation of Children and Young People

The Council of Europe has developed a framework for the participation of children and young people in decision-making processes that affect their lives. This framework emphasizes the importance of empowering young people to participate actively in society and have their voices heard on issues that concern them.

Regional Mechanisms

In addition to these international mechanisms, there are also regional mechanisms for the protection of youth rights. For example, the African Youth Charter, adopted by the African Union in 2006, sets out the rights and freedoms of young people in Africa and calls on member states to take measures to promote and protect these rights.

Conclusion

International mechanisms for the protection of youth rights play a crucial role in ensuring that young people are able to fully enjoy their rights and participate actively in society. By ratifying and implementing these instruments, states can demonstrate their commitment to promoting the well-being and development of young people around the world.

REFERENCES

1. United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) The Convention on the Rights of the Child was adopted by the UN General Assembly on November 20, 1989 and entered into force in September 1990
2. International Labour Organization (ILO) Conventions, The International Labour Organization (ILO) was established in 1919. Since 1946, the ILO has been a specialized agency of the United Nations.
3. World Health Organization (WHO) Guidelines. The World Health Organization was founded in 1948 with its main office in Geneva (Switzerland).
4. Council of Europe Framework for the Participation of Children and Young People (2016-2021)
5. African Youth Charter. The African Youth Charter was signed at the seventh regular meeting of the African Union, held in Banjul (Gambia) July 2, 2006.